

FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF STITCHED STIFFENED COMPOSITE PANEL WITH IMPACT DAMAGE

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ABSTRACT: Textile structural composites with through-the-thickness reinforcement are promising materials for aircraft structural applications. In this work, the compressive fatigue behavior of stitched, stiffened panels with clearly visible impact damage (CVFD) on the flange has been studied experimentally. The panels having two blade stiffeners are composed of 3501-6 epoxy resin and AS4-3k plain weave fabrics stitched with Kevlar 2790 yarn. The panels were impacted at the flange area before fatigue tests. These impacted panels were tested in constant amplitude compression fatigue loading and modified Transport Wing Standard Test (TWIST) spectrum fatigue loading. In all constant fatigue tests, cracks emanated from the impact site and propagated towards the stiffener. The stiffener stopped the crack for most of the panel's fatigue life. Once the crack penetrated the stiffener, the panel failed within a few cycles. However, under spectrum fatigue loading, the panels could suddenly crash without visible sign of damage evolution.

Key words: stitching, textile composite, fatigue, Resin film infusion

INSTRUCTION

Composite materials have been already used in the aerospace industry for a couple of decades. However, composite laminates suffer from low damage tolerance because of their high sensitivity to out-of-plane failure resulting from low interlaminar fracture toughness. To alleviate this shortcoming, a promising approach is through the incorporation of mechanical reinforcement in the thickness direction, such as through-the thickness stitching. Recent studies by Dow et al. [1-2] have shown that stitching of conventional laminates can increase damage tolerance to the level comparable to the toughened resin systems but at a lower cost.

It is clearly that stitching increases interlaminar fracture toughness, which has been reported by some investigators [3-4]. However, The effect of stitching on static strength is controversial. Khan and Mouritz [5] reported no change in tensile strength of stitched glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) laminates, and Harris et al. [6] reached the same conclusion for carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates. However, Dexter and Funk [3] and Su [7] measured reductions of up to 25% in tensile strength of CFRP laminates due to stitching.

Sharma and Sankar [8-9] performed compression after impact tests on stitched uniweave laminates containing implanted delaminations. Their findings indicate that stitching is very effective in retaining the compression strength after impact (CSAI) as long as the stitch yarn has a minimum stiffness and strength. They concluded that the stitch density is of greater importance than the stiffness and strength of the stitch yarn. However, they also found that stitching causes approximately 10% drop in compressive strength. Dow and Smith [1] and Liu [10] examined the effects of stitching density and stitch pattern on impact damage pattern. They found that the shape of delamination area changed significantly with the stitching pattern, indicating an effective role of stitching in preventing delamination.

Khan and Mouritz [5] investigated the effects of stitch orientation and stitch density on the S-N curve of GFRP laminates under tension fatigue. Interlaminar fracture properties were improved three times after stitching, but the ultimate tensile strength remained unchanged and fatigue resistance was reduced considerably, particularly at low fatigue stresses. Fatigue failure occurred at the stitches because of the damage incurred on the glass fibers during stitching. Moon et al. [11] investigated post-impact fatigue response of stitched carbon/epoxy laminates to find that stitching resulted in twice the fatigue strength of the baseline unstitched laminates. In another study by Portanova et al. [12] comparing the effectiveness of stitching and matrix toughening under compression fatigue, stitching did not show any advantage in the presence of a notched hole.

The contradictory effects of stitching observed on fatigue behavior and static strength warrants further work to fully characterize the fatigue durability of stitched composites. Moreover, while these studies have provided information on the coupon-level effect of stitching, the potential of structure-level benefits still remain to be ascertained. Thus, the objective of this paper is to investigate the compression fatigue properties of stiffened panels with impact damage at flange area. The blade stiffened composite panel is a common airframe structure element.

MANUFACTURING COMPOSITE PANELS

AS4 fibers and Hercules 3501-6 resin system were used in the current study for making the panels. The AS4 fabric and 3501-6 epoxy resin are well characterized and widely used [13-15]. A 1600-denier Kevlar 29 thread was selected for stitching and a 400-denier Kevlar 29 thread for the bobbin. Further details on the materials are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Materials used in the present study

Material	Description
Fabric	Hexcel 282, AS4 plain weave fabric, 3k yarns, 12.5 yarns/25.4mm
Resin	Hexcel 3501-6
Stitch Yarn	Kevlar 29, needle thread 1600 denier, bobbin thread 400 denier

Figure 1 shows the design of a two-blade stiffened panel. The stiffener spacing of 15.24 cm is comparable to those studied by Starnes Jr. et al. [16], Madan [17] and Stevens et al. [18]. Both the length and width of the panel are 25.4 cm each. The skin consists of 13 layers of fabric and the stiffener has 12 layers. The flange area consists of the skin and one-half of the stiffener. The lay-up sequences are as follows:

Skin: $[0/90, \pm 45, 0/90, \pm 45, 0/90]_T$
 Stiffener: $[\pm 45, 0/90, \pm 45, 0/90, \pm 45, 0/90]_{2S}$
 Flange: $[0/90, \pm 45, 0/90, 0/90, \pm 45, 0/90, \pm 45]_T$

Carbon fiber preforms were stitched on a JUKI 2000 sewing machine with guides on its working platform. The stitching speed was 18 cm per minute for the modified lock stitching, and both the stitch pitch and spacing were 3.175 mm based. 30 tows of 3k yarn AS4 carbon fibers were inserted into the gap at the skin-stiffener joint using a hooked wire. A stitched fiber preform is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. A blade-stiffened panel

Figure 2. A stitched preform with stiffeners

The stitched preform was placed into the mold containing the resin film, and the vacuumed assembly was placed in an autoclave and cured. Dimensions of the manufactured panel were 54.61 cm x 30.48 cm x 4.23 cm. After machining overall dimensions of each specimen were 25.4 cm x 25.4 cm with two 2.54-cm stiffeners. The detail geometries of the panel shown in Figure 1 are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Nominal dimensions of stiffened panels

Lpanel	254.0 mm	Tskin	2.86 mm
Ls	247.7 mm	Triser	2.64 mm
Le	3.18 mm	Hs	25.4 mm
Wpanel	254.0 mm	We	76.2 mm
Ws	152.4 mm	Wt	4.18 mm

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Impact tests were performed according to the method recommended by SACMA, SRM 2-88 [19]. Impact loading was applied using a drop weight on a Dynatup 8250 drop-weight impact testing machine with a 4.3- kg indenter having a 12.7-mm diameter tup. For impact and subsequent compression testing, the panel was held between top and bottom end plates having a groove. The panel was inserted into the grooves of end plates and secured using Cerrobend® alloy having a melting temperature of 70° C. The panel assembly was placed on the base of the Dynatup for impact testing with the end plates providing support [20-23]. The energy of impact on a flange was 30 J in order to generate a clearly visible damage on stitched panel. A clearly visible damage is dent depth greater than 2.54 mm or broken fibers, and it is expected to carry full design limit load. The impact points were on the flat skin side of the panel. Typical X-ray radiograph and C-SCAN image of impact-damaged area are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Non-destructive evaluation of flange impact on panel, C-SCAN (a) and (b), X-ray (c)

Static compression tests were performed on a 500-kN Instron test frame at a displacement rate of 1.27 mm/min. The panel and fixture system are illustrated in Figure 4. The resulting gage length of the panel was approximately 24.13 cm. Omega 900 series data acquisition modules were used to record strains, lateral displacement, top displacement, and applied load. Strain gages were placed back to back at the center of the panel to capture a bifurcation point during loading. Compression fatigue tests were also performed on the 500-kN Instron test frame at a frequency ranging from 0.05 to 0.3 Hz depending on the load levels. The same fixtures and gripping method as in static compression tests were used in fatigue tests. The five highest loading levels of the Transport Wing Standard Test (TWIST) spectrum for spectrum fatigue were selected for the constant-amplitude fatigue tests. In TWIST spectrum illustrated in Table 3, each block consists of ten alternating loads ranging from 0.222 to 1.6 times the flight mean load, representing 4,000 flights. A repetition of ten blocks represents a life cycle or 40,000 flights. The two lowest load levels of TWIST spectrum have been deleted for the present study to shorten test time since they were found to have negligible effect on coupon specimens in an earlier study. Because of the testing difficulty, any excursion into tension was also truncated. So a modified TWIST spectrum was used for spectrum fatigue test. Loading was applied in the decreasing order of magnitude. The fatigue stress ratio R was kept at infinity for both constant amplitude fatigue and spectrum fatigue tests.

Table 3. Modified twist spectrum

X parameter	Alternating Load, X Flight Mean Load									
	1.6	1.5	1.3	1.1	0.99	0.84	0.68	0.53	0.37*	0.22*
No. of cycles	1	2	5	18	52	152	800	4170	34800	358665

* These two load levels were deleted.

Schematic Diagram of the Specimen-Fixture Assembly

Figure 4. Specimen-Fixture Assembly

Table 4. Summary of static compression test, stitched stiffened panels

Specimen #	Initial Impact	Buckling load [MPa]	Failure load [MPa]
SP2b	N/A	79.8	180.8
SP5a	N/A	93.20	131.0
SP3a	N/A	88.3	181.8
SP5b	Flange dent	66.1	168.6
SP3b	Flange dent	72.4	187.7
SP4a	Flange dent	76.3	181.7

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Static Compression Strength of Stiffened Panels

Three panels with clearly visible flange damage (CVFD) were tested to measure the compressive strength after impact (CSAI). Static compressive strength also was obtained from tests on three undamaged panels. As shown in Table 4, the average buckling loads of the undamaged, and CVFD panels are 87.1MPa and 71.6MPa, respectively. A reduction of buckling load was observed for CVFD case compared to undamaged case. Based on experimental observation, both types of panels exhibited a predominant buckling mode shape resembled a half sine wave deformation. The average compression strength were 181.4 and 179.3 MPa for undamaged and CVFD panels, respectively.

Compression Constant Amplitude Fatigue Behavior

Panels with an impact-damaged at a flange edge were tested in constant-amplitude fatigue to failure. Five higher stress levels from the TWIST loading spectrum are taken as the constant fatigue stress levels. They are 81.4%, 80.3%, 73.6%, 70.7% and 65.8% of average CSAI. All these compression loads are higher than the panel's buckling load. Two panels are tested for each load level. The fatigue life diagrams for the panels are found in Figure 5. The fatigue lives of these panels decreased with increasing compression loading. The relationship between the compression stress range and the number of fatigue cycles to failure fits a linear relationship in the log coordinate graph. The best straight-line satisfies the stress versus life curve was obtained by linear regression analysis. The stress versus life function is described as

$$\sigma = \beta N^C \quad (1)$$

where σ is compression stress range, N is fatigue cycles to failure. The parameters associated with the panel's fatigue life (fatigue coefficient β and fatigue exponent C) are determined to be

0.8838 and -0.0213 respectively. This function is similar to the Coffin-Manson relationship for low cycle fatigue life of materials. If fatigue limit is set as 10^7 cycles, the fatigue limit stress can be deduced to be 115 MPa. However, this function should be used with caution because of the large scatter in fatigue life.

The fatigue properties of the impacted panels were summarized in Table 5. When the loading was higher than 80% CSAI, sudden collapse could happen on the stiffened panels. Panels SP6a and SP7a, two of four specimens tested under the load higher than 80% CSAI failed at the first cycle. During the lowest load (around 65% CSAI) in constant fatigue tests, the fatigue life of a specimen reached to nearly 10,000 cycles. It reveals that the fifth load level of TWIST spectrum loads is not negligible to predict the fatigue strength of the panels. In other words, the higher five stress levels in TWIST spectrum can not be deleted in an accelerated test scheme for accurately predicting panel fatigue life. It also implies that the critical load for unlimited fatigue life should be below 65% CSAI for the impacted flange panel case.

Figure 5. Constant-fatigue lives of flange impacted panels

Table 5. Constant-amplitude fatigue results: stitched stiffened panels

Specimen ID	Max. Comp. Stress, MPa	Loading frequency, Hz	Number of Cycles to Failure	Causes of Failure
SP6a	143.4	0.05	1	Premature failure
SP12a	143.4	0.05	2111	Damage induced stiffener failure
SP7a	138.3	0.05	1	Premature failure
SP8a	139.4	0.10	35	Damage induced stiffener failure
SP9a	127.6	0.20	306	Damage induced stiffener failure
SP7b	127.6	0.20	1606	Impact caused stiffener damage
SP9b	116.5	0.30	3005	Damage induced stiffener failure
SP8b	115.5	0.30	26273	Damage induced stiffener failure
SP10a	110.9	0.30	2200	Defective panel, not fully resin infiltrated
SP11a	110.9	0.30	9474	Damage induced stiffener failure

In spite of load levels, the damage evaluation processes in flange-damaged panels are similar as shown in Figure 6. In most panels, two cracks grew normal to the loading from the damage site, for example the two cracks on Sp8a shown in Figure 7(a). These cracks propagated intermittently such that they extended during one load cycle but then stopped for several cycles. It is anticipated

that the stitch caused the going and stopping phenomenon of these cracks. The crack slowed down and stopped when it approached a stitch. The crack speeded up after the stitch yarn fractured. It is nature that these cracks grew faster at higher stresses. The stiffener with the damaged flange arrested the crack from getting closer to it, and it was interesting that the crack on the other side seemed to stop as well. It took most of the fatigue cycles for the crack to extend into the stiffener, and once the crack entered the stiffener, the panel failed within a few cycles because another stiffener could not stand the compression load along, illustrated in Figure 7(b).

Figure 6. Constant amplitude fatigue cracks growing on flange impact panels, (a) SP8a under 80.3 % CSAI, (b) SP9a under 73.6 % CSAI, and (c) SP9b under 70.9 % CSAI. Crack one towards stiffener, crack two towards the center of a panel.

Figure 7. Flange damaged specimen SP8a under constant amplitude fatigue loading 80.3 % CSAI, (a) crack initiated from impact point and stopped at the stiffener, (b) specimen crashed when the crack went through the stiffener.

Compression Spectrum Fatigue Behavior

TWIST spectrum fatigue load is modified by deleting any tensile loads and two lowest load levels. The modified TWIST spectrum loadings were performed on three panels with the impact damage on the flange. The mean load level of the spectrum loadings is 34% of the CSAI corresponding to a stress level of 55.3 MPa. The maximum compression load level is 81.4% of CSAI.

The test results are listed in Table 6. Specimen SP1b suddenly crashed at the highest load of the 10th block. The crack that broke the panel to two half parts went through the impact site. Specimen SP4b were scanned ultrasonically at an interval of several fatigue blocks. The C-scan yields information on the extension of fatigue damages. Examining C-SCAN graphs taken prior to failure and failure history can deduce the progression of the damage. Figure 8 shows C-SCAN images of SP4b at the end of 5th, 8th, 13th block of spectrum fatigue load. It indicates that the damage area around the impact site grew larger during spectrum fatigue loadings even though

there was no visible sign on the panel. However, the damage around the impact site of SP4b did not fatally cause the panel to crash. Both stiffeners fractured one by one at the highest load of the 16th block. Unfortunately, C-scan could not show the damage evolution in stiffeners. It was noted that there was no visible crack around the impacted point at this time even after the two stiffeners failed. Then, the specimen endured lower load levels. Two cracks propagating from impacted site were observed when reaching the 20th cycle in the sixth load level. The cracks stopped, and restart growing at the 199th cycle of the seventh level but crashed at the 200th cycle. Specimen SP6b survived up to 20th block of load. For the two broken panels, they both failed within one block of loading so the spectrum fatigue behaviors of flange-impacted panels belong to the sudden collapse model.

Table 6. Spectrum fatigue lives for the three flange damaged composite panels

Specimen ID	Number of Blocks Completed	Load Level at Failure	Fatigue Failure Behavior
SP1b	10	1st	Stiffeners and skin crashed at same time with a big sound
SP4b	16	7th	Stiffeners broke one by one with two loud sounds. Stiffeners broke earlier than skin
SP6b	20	No failure	Survived 20 th block

Figure 8. C-scan image at (a) 5th, (b) 8th, (c) 13th block of spectrum fatigue load for specimen SP4. Impact point got bigger and stiffener got wider. Total fatigue life was 16 blocks of load.

CONCLUSIONS

The fatigue durability characteristics of stitched stiffened panels with clearly visible impact damage on the flange have been investigated experimentally. The results are summarized as follows.

For CVFD panels under constant amplitude fatigue loading, there were two cracks initiated from the impacted dent and grew vertically along the load direction. When one of the cracks reached the base of stiffener, it stopped by the stiffener. It took most of the fatigue life for the crack to go through the stiffener. Once the stiffener failed to seize the crack, the panel would crash within few fatigue cycles.

Under spectrum fatigue loading, the CVFD panels could suddenly crash at the highest compression loading of the spectrum loading without visible sign of damage evolution. The stiffeners could fail earlier than the skin.

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